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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Monteiro_240402203_June_2024_Global_Lipidomic			
Document creation date		09/16/2025		Principal investigator		MTH-Metatoul-Lipidomique	
Institution		I2MC-INSERM		Corresponding Email		lipidomique.i2mc@inserm.fr	
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted		Clinical		No	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		1-phase system		pH adjustment		None	
1-phase system		Isopropanol		Special conditions		2 punches was extracted	

Were internal standards used?	Yes	Deposition method	Manual pipetting
Internal standards used	Home made LipidoMix (mixture of internal standards, one per sub-classes of lipids)		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Number of separation dimensions	One dimension
Separation type 1	SFC	Separation mode 1 (liquid)	NP
Detector	Mass spectrometer	MS type	QTOF
MS vendor	Waters	Ion source	ESI
MS Level	MS ¹	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹	High resolution
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS ¹	18000	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS ¹	5
Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹	Centroid mode	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank
Quality control	No		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	No	Accuracy	No
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request		

Sample Descriptions

Dried blood Spot / Human / Dried blood Spot

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Sample homogenization	No
Temperature handling original sample	Unknown	Instant sample preparation	No
Storage temperature	Room temperature	Additives	None

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) CAR / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CAR	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	Isotope correction at MS ¹	No
MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes	Background check at MS ¹	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Limit of detection	Signal threshold	RT verified by standard	Yes
Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No	Model for separation prediction	No
Lipid Identification Software	MzMine	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

1) CAR / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
CAR 18:1_D3		CAR	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
FA 17:0		FA	

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

3) DG[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

3) DG[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
	Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	
	(1,2) DG 24:0	(1,2) DG	
	(1,3) DG 24:0	(1,3) DG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

4) TG[M+NH₄]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH ₄] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

4) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
TG 17:0/17:1/17:0-D5		TG	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

5) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

5) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPC 11:0		LPC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

6) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No

Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

6) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
LPE 13:0		LPE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

7) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

7) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PC (13:0/13:0)		PC	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

8) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

8) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PE (12:0/12:0)		PE	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

9) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H] ⁻
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

9) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PG 24:0		PG	

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

10) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

10) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PI 15:0-18:1-d7		PI	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

11) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M-H]-
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

11) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
PS 24:0		PS	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

12) Cer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

12) Cer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Cer 30:1,02		Cer	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

13) HexCer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No

Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

13) HexCer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
HexCer 30:1,O2		HexCer	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

14) Hex2Cer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

14) Hex2Cer[M+H-H₂O]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Hex2Cer 30:1,O2		Hex2Cer	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

15) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

15) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
SM 30:1,O2		SM	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

16) CE[M+Na]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+Na] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

16) CE[M+Na]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
CE 17:0		CE	

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		

17) FC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FC	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+H] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
RT verified by standard	Yes	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Model for separation prediction	No	Lipid Identification Software	MzMine
Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Lock mass correction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes

17) FC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ¹			
Internal standard		Endogenous subclass	
Cer 30:1,O2		Free Cholesterol	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	MzMine
Batch correction	No		